

Article

Microeconomics Impacts of COVID-19 Pandemic: Media Analysis

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Abstract

COVID-19 known as a novel Coronavirus in entire world when first case of acute pneumonia found in Wuhan, China in 2019 with severe viral infection. Coronavirus have been still able to maintain its fear and panic among in every country and every individual. At a side where macroeconomics is dealing with whole major changes in economy and on other side microeconomy is usually tells the common attitude, behavior and perception of people in particular region for COVID-19. Before invention of vaccine for Coronavirus, communication channels, media, religious societies had shown a major role to make fear in local people's mind and these all information had been leading the worldwide panic and critical situations. Although a survey revealed that media and all communication channels were responsible for made panic among population and situations had gone wrong. Despite following precautions and administrative orders by all individual but sufferings became worst. From recent studies it has concluded that microeconomics of World's status in terms of COVID-19 has become negative and from past two years every firm and individual has been going through a major loss.

Keywords: COVID-19, pandemic, microeconomics, macroeconomics, socio-economic, poverty

Introduction:

Microeconomic is the study of economic that deals with the three individual analytical variables of economics such as micro static analysis, micro comparative static analysis, and micro dynamic analysis. If anyone do research on the microeconomics at first he think some topics generally, microeconomics depends on the basis of these topics such as production, stock, demand, opportunity cost, market equilibrium which forms of competition and profit maximization ,comparative advantage economic equilibrium income effect, consumer surplus overview and economic of scale .As a learner, one should avoid the disconcert with the microeconomics and macroeconomics of two parts of economics because they deals economy in some different way. There are two parts of economy, one is the micro-economy and the other is the macro-economy. One is complementary to the another. Microeconomics usually focuses on actions of individual agents like consumers, households, businesses and works, regarding allocation of scare resource within an economy. On the other

hand Macroeconomics refers to broad issues like unemployment level, GDP, inflation, interest rates, government deficits, monetary policy and fiscal policy. Coronavirus is a virus that is surrounded by a protein coating called ribonucleic acid (RNA) belongs to the genus Coronaviridae of the class Nidovirales. The virus enters humans from a variety of objects used by the environment and grows in the throat and lungs. Coronavirus is a virus that is surrounded by a protein coating called ribonucleic acid (RNA) belonging to the genus Coronaviridae of the class Nidovirales. SARS-COV2 virus enters the human body from a variety of objects used by the environment and grows in the throat and lungs. At first it causes colds in the human lungs. The virus first spreads through the infected patient to the environment and is transmitted through the environment, human sneezing-coughing and human-human contact. In humans, the virus kills people by causing short-term fatal diseases on the respiratory tract. To control the proliferation of virus whole across the world government of each countries are likely to have some lockdowns.

Fig.1.SARS-COV2 Structure

In 2020, heads of government of different countries have been issuing lockdowns for

months for a suitable vaccine, while others have issued shutdowns. Strict health policies were

adopted in almost all countries of the world. The World Health Organization has issued social distance. In compliance with the health policy issued by the World Health Organization, in the reality of global health, the heads of government have imposed restrictions on the import and export of production and exportable resources. Reviewing the history of the period, it can be seen that the main and primary reason for the spread of this deadly disease is due to non-adoption of social distance health policy, non-stop of import and export, movement of people.

As a result, the global economy is shrinking day by day, which will shrink by 2.4% in 2020. 12.5% of the world's third tier daily wage earners will experience extreme economic depression. Emerging economies will take this situation more intensely, even more time will elapse to restore this state of the economy, and the pace of this recovery process will slow down. The continuous rise in commodity prices has caused depression and stagnation in the minds of the people since the global corona virus hit. It is expected that if the global COVID-19 situation improves, economic recovery will be possible by 2022. It is estimated that if economic recovery is not possible, the unemployment rate, which was 5.2% in the 2019 survey, will rise to 10% by mid-2020 and more to 2021. And in order to cope with the downturn in the economy, almost every country in the world has to take measures to maintain a balance between health care, socio-economic status and livelihoods. For the first time since 1990, public life is falling below the poverty line, according to a 2020 UN research report. This means that the steps taken by the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals are going to be threatened by the Poverty Alleviation 2030 Corona virus. The report states that the negative impact of Covid-19 on global poverty and socio-economic conditions through the per capita contraction calculation is a global integrated multidisciplinary review. Low, Medium and High global declines of 5%, 10%, 20% and US \$ 1.90,

US \$ 3.20 and US \$ 5.50 are shown in three international poverty line expenditures. According to a report edited by the IFAD, about 1.4 billion people in the world live in extreme poverty, including underdeveloped and developing countries on other continents, including Africa. Where many African countries and a certain ethnic group in those countries are under the Poverty Alleviation Action Plan. Meanwhile, people in areas where the COVID-19 epidemic has taken shape will reach such a low level of poverty that it will take about 30 years to get out of there. According to a government report in 2016, it is estimated that when poverty in these regions reaches a record low, those countries will have to cut revenue by 20% or cut national spending by 20%. On the other hand, in order to implement this policy, about 42.0-57.0 crore people have to lose their jobs and live in extreme poverty (Sumner et al 2020). In our paper, we discuss the emergence of COVID-19, and its harmful effects on individual and family life, health risks, social life, state life, socio-economic and microeconomics, and famine, hunger. The depth of hunger and poverty can be reduced, socio-economic and damaged microeconomics can be recovered.

Phenomenon of Poverty:

The European country, Latvia believes that asking or giving help to someone is tantamount to extreme humiliation, rudeness and indifference because the feeling of dependence on others is nothing more than a blow to one's own independent existence. This means that its simple definition of poverty is to create a situation similar to poverty. Different international organizations have defined poverty in different ways. Behind such a definition there is again a direct or indirect impetus to legal processes. Poverty was once defined in the General Assembly session in such a way that the cause of the violation of human dignity is basically the degradation of humanity by creating

opportunities to choose and deny poverty. According to the United Nations, a number of different nations have reflected poverty as a state of "deprivation" due to *poor health, poor access to housing, poor housing and lack of proper education*. That is, poverty means the need for all the basic abilities without which a person cannot effectively enter society and participate in successful leadership. In addition to this, it is enough to bear the expenses of the family. But there is lack of access to schools and hospitals, lack of cultivable land and repeated cultivation of the same crop over and over again. In pandemic times even lack of extra support or lack of revenue or savings means poverty of individual's family and exclusion community means insecurity powerlessness, lack of natural resources where no person or his marginal environment is harsh, adequate use of safe drinking water even if there is adequate sanitization, sensitivity to violent communities without any consideration or knowledge. In our best experience we can say that poverty is an ongoing flow of events that deprives people of basic necessities acceptable in their lives. Incidents like the vicious cycle of poverty in human life are relative which can consume at any time in life. On the other hand, second class poverty means that personal, socio-economic and basic needs such as other clothing, housing, education, medical care, etc., do not change according to the meaning in a complete way. There are also other causes of poverty such as weak economic system and planning, colonial past history of not having a heroic system of governance or dictatorship or good governance, superstitious bigotry of tribal and state management without adopting economic plan according to conservative social system, there could also be many other reasons. Used from different perspectives to make poverty easier to understand. Usually published by international organizations like the United Nations. The most important new indicators in the research of the

World Bank and the World Economic Forum are the work of Barros et al. 2006. This Brazilian study set 48 indicators organized into six levels, namely: vulnerability, lack of access to knowledge, lack of access work, lack of resources, child development work and homelessness (American Journal of Economics 2020).

Challenges of COVID-19 Pandemic and Multidimensional Poverty:

This pandemic leads to have different experience to world, about mass disease transmission in upcoming era, vast change in technology over 100 years. There is high spread of deadly COVID-19 disease and vaccination reach is slow and not properly curable, so food scarcity and affects to normal livelihoods, leads to spread of crimes, corruption, expansion of terrorist power (Ahmed & Buheji 2018). Influenced by COVID-19, there are in general three types of poverty, or the three types of poor are most affected by COVID-19. Income issue increased for complete instability in society and the state, resulting in poverty. The middle class poor will fall under this category because of the difficulty of not being able to find a full-time or part-time job and then borrowing. The third category is the poor who are less affected where the basic human needs of food, clothing, clean water, health and treatment are lacking, while their shelter, education and other facilities will remain almost unchanged. In general, poverty is a definition, or subject, defined by various indicators, which is known and controlled in multidimensional indices, and not in any single index. When human society faces poverty in a pandemic, economic factors are seen as the only reason to deal with it. There are also types of poverty and some ownership rights such as food, clothing, housing, education, health care, medical treatment. Analyzing all these issues will increase our thinking and analysis ability, how the spread epidemic spreads prestige in the world. Although it is different in some

developed countries. How are you and the people around you realizing the effects of Covid-19 epidemic and epidemic in human life? People around you who have not been able to meet their basic needs in life, and those who have not been able to meet their basic needs throughout life, you feel that you should be deprived of the basic needs of life. Do you think that poverty is being created only for them or that they are responsible for it? Do you think they are a disability for family society and the state? Yes, now is the time for change, because the only concern is that the leaders of the world are ruling the world with the COVID-19 mitigation measures. Where more deprivation has to be acknowledged to provide for the daily necessities and basic necessities of life in order to survive. Needless to say, inadequate income or failure to create income opportunities will lead to further deprivation of life (Buheji 2019). Poverty is a relative matter that changes with the passage of time. Individuals or people living in a particular region may experience perpetual poverty over time. Poverty is sometimes defined in such a way that it does not find the power of day and the power of night (Shilbach et al 2016). However, it is important to note that in all realities, there is a need to create opportunities for the poor, the poor to have all kinds of resources, or the responsibility to manage autonomous development activities so that they do not end up in failure (Buheji 2019). Today, with the mere mention of web and social media benefits, people can expect to see a huge trend from the poor. Who is responsible for controlling the backgrounds behind it? A group of privileged people are responsible for misleading the society during its leadership, misleading the poor without proper education, and as a result they do things that are humiliated by many through their actions. Power of nationwide interim unveiling in Asian countries. And its fundamentals are social, health related economic status and social basis. Again, based on these foundations, poverty can be identified or

marked in different ways. For example, the first reason to feel poor is lack of income, secondly the financial condition will be determined based on the physical condition (Buheji 2019).

World Poverty status before COVID-19:

Case: Asia (India)

Since the worldwide outbreak of COVID-19, it has been declared epidemic initially. With that in mind, according to the Epidemic Control and Control Act, 1897, passed by the Indian Ministry of Health and the Department of Health, a number of educational institutions of all kinds in the country also declared a number of commercial establishments and offices under various ministries closed. India is the first country in the world to understand the impact of the Corona virus. The Prime Minister of India issued a 14-hour nationwide lockdown on March 22, 2020. The government announced these closures so that the virus could not enter the country with goods and passengers by any means of transportation. The lockdown policy issued by the government observed by all citizens equally, the government announced that the lockdown policy will be relaxed, or lifted by April 14. But due to the negligence of the people, the Corona situation in India was deteriorating. As a result, it was extended till May 3. In a report published on The Oxford Publishing's Government Tracker site, it published a report on the role of governments in different countries in mitigating Covid-19 and the various aspects and steps to be taken. India's Prime Minister Narendra Modi is on the top of the list in report. The second lockdown has been slightly relaxed with a few minor changes. In areas of India where the Covid-19 pandemic and epidemiology, the risk of these attacks or any of the influential areas in the social distance to the green signal economic activities were announced to continue. In this context, the question arises as to how India will find a solution to the problems

of the poor in the society and the poor in different parts of the country Covid19, or to respond to the problems by publishing a report (Deccanharald 2020). Hotspots are one of the most unpopular sectors in India. The informal branch is the only source of income for about 90% of India's population. 90% of this population includes rickshaw pullers, migrant workers, sharecroppers and marginal farmers. This huge population has no jobs, no religious holidays, no government holidays, they are deprived of all domestic facilities. Not getting all the benefits, they live in a state of helplessness (Economic Times, 2020).

Case: Africa (Ghana, Nigeria and Kenya)

Many developing countries and poor countries in the world, especially in Asia and Africa, are heading towards long-term and fatal outcome in the hands of Covid-19. Many countries will have to endure long-term poverty because their development activities will be halted due to lack of funds of World Bank (2020). In fact, those who live under economic, social, health and educational services will have to bear the brunt of the Corona virus epidemic worldwide in 2020. According to the World Bank (2000), poverty is the lack of appetite and hunger, lack of shelter, inability to be admit to hospital in severe cases, not being able to get higher education, not being able to read and write, not being able to work, not getting job opportunities, fear of the future. And to show the idea and tendency to survive in a short time. This life information is found to be similar to the life of more than 80% of Africans. About half of all people in Africa live on \$ 2.5 a day or less. Research has shown that the main cause of human poverty is the capitalist economy. Africa has been plagued by poverty for several years. Man-made internal and international conflicts, wars, and poverty have plagued the continent since human evolution. Main idea is that the sun of freedom has not risen in the sky of this continent since the beginning of creation. Epidemic Covid-19 attacks, recurrence

factors leads to pandemic situations are responsible for deaths, and threats to living communities. The African nation, which has been in slavery for a long time, has not developed knowledge of technology, science and art. And Africa is one of the main and permanent causes of poverty. The main causes of persistent poverty in this part of the world are dysfunctional leadership, poor governance of corrupt people, bribery and corruption, lack of vision and leadership. According to the World Bank, people living in the sub Saharan Africa on less than \$1.9 a day. The number of people living below the international poverty line has risen from 54.3% in 1990 to 41.0% in 2013. In 1990 it was 276 million, which increased to 388.7 million people in 2013 (Anyanwu 2017). About 82% poor people who live in rural areas, whose main source of income agriculture, a significant number of the rural poor provide employment to others in their areas by creating opportunities for agriculture and farming. Every year in Africa, high child mortality due to malnutrition, short life, various diseases, illiteracy, ambiguity around life, etc. Various diseases like Kovid-19 will take the form of epidemics. When a poor person is asked who is poor and how they feel about poverty. The man says "Don't ask me what poverty is? Because you met it outside my house. Look at the house and count the number of holes. Look at my utensils and look I wear what sort of clothes. See everything and write what you see, what you see is called poverty.

Case: South America

Before the coronavirus epidemic in 2020, Latin American countries Brazil and Argentina have already faced economic crises. This region of Latin America has created political and economic instability crises, mainly because of the similarities between life itself and the poor. According to the World Bank (2017), Despite Brazil's economic growth has been made possible by the experience of the actions of the Brazilian

people over the past decade. A review of Brazil's historical history reveals that Brazil was the country with the most fragile economy. Brazil's population is responsible for creating poverty in their country. The best of the main features of poverty is the structural condition, in which the population represents an unequal relationship for income distribution (Oliveira et al., 2017; Silva et al., 2017). A review of official data shows that, in 2016, until about, as many as 52 million people live in Brazil in poor economic conditions or in poor conditions, and 13.3 million people lived below the extreme poverty line (Ibex 2017). In terms of inequality, currently, 1% Brazil's population enjoys 28% of the country's wealth (World Bank, 2017). Outbreaks appear to be exacerbated during the last few years. Brazil is already facing a strong economic problem. The economic crisis has to be dealt with because of the political crisis, which is being identified as the main reason. Unemployment is on the rise as a result of labor laws, loss of rights and consequent layoffs, not creating new employment opportunities (Brazilian Institute of Geography and Statistic, IBGE 2020). In terms of economic evolution, the number of poor people in Brazil increased from 25.7% of the total population in 2016, according to data released by the World Bank. And increased to 26.5% in 2017. This is followed by children and adolescents aged 0 to 14 years. Cost per day is 5 5.5, increasing from 42.9% during this period to 43.4%. South America, in general, has failed miserably to reduce poverty .

Case: Europe

The countries of the European Union have been developing with the formation of the Union. As a result, the Union countries have raised themselves as GDP growth countries. The key to GDP growth is technological development, and infrastructural development (American Journal of Economics 2020). The main source of economic growth in Europe is trade. Europe is a prosperous

continent of the world. And the main goal of the European Session is to bring economic development, equality and poverty alleviation. The topic discussed in the EU Parliament is economic approved a spike in 2007 to resolve the economic crisis. Poverty and economic inequality in Europe, which is already there. Considered as the main problem (Laserf 2016). Definition of poverty given by EU (2010), accepted definition of poverty all over the world. Europeans believe that according to the European Union (EU 2011), poverty is relative, where the income of a family as a person or consideration and the total wealth of that family is not socially accepted or if a family does not have social acceptance, and social leadership. They are deprived of the opportunity to participate. Where there are people, poverty will come relatively. European countries that refer to poverty as relative, (Council of Europe). According to a 2000 World Health Organization report, 25% of all children in southern and Eastern Europe live below the extreme poverty line. The rate of social neglect peaked in 2005 due to poverty in Europe. However, in 2017, of the 113 million people living in the poverty line, 22.4% of the EU population was at risk of social neglect due to poverty. 1 in 5 of the total population living in Europe describes 3 types of poverty from their experience of poverty. First, the deadly effects of financial poverty, such as social deprivation and family unrest. (EUROSTAT, Europe 2020 Index – Poverty and social exclusion). The economic crisis of 2008 took a serious turn in 2009. Due to which the number of poverty in Europe is increasing. In Europe About 300 Millions are affected by the crisis, which accounts for 29.6% of the total poor living at risk of poverty. They have been socially, economically, familial deprived and they have been affected in different ways. The 6 million poor people who were exposed to total poverty were affected by three factors influencing poverty (European Union 2019).

Global Poverty Status estimation due to COVID-19 Pandemic:

Due to COVID-19 pandemic estimation of global poverty increment is quite challenging. If estimation is done by using general equilibrium models or explore about all countries that what is going to happen next, fixed amount of growth rate declines and no accuracy in output. In this paper used World Bank approach of all survey data of household and 166 countries growth projection to forecast new normal poverty (Daniel et al., 2020).

From Online tool of World Bank for estimation of Global Poverty which is named as PovcalNet data is extracted. From 2019 to 2020 there is increment of around 8.2-8.6% (approx 632-665 million people) of world’s population who lives on less than \$1.90 per day. Therefore, in this extreme poverty of around 49 millions of individuals are going to see if same crises continues in upcoming years so to overcome this socio-economic loss there is need to expand more social safety nets across developing countries.

Fig: 2. Represents differentiation between expected to be elimination of poverty historical line and impact of COVID-19 on Global Poverty

**The Impact of Covid-19 (Coronavirus) On Global Poverty:
On Poverty communities Socio-economic Impacts of COVID-19**

Among most of the countries COVID-19 economic impact represents three possible scenarios that are labour productivity shock (in 2020, approx 1.4% labour productivity decrement), total factor productivity shock (reduction of global GDP by 1%), trade shock (trade cost increment on average of 5%, provokes

global economic growth cost of about 1%) (Vos et al., 2020).

Continent- Asia:

In Asia among list of developing countries India get prior name; lockdown itself affected a lot. Major issue with migrant workers, In 2020 Supreme Court informed by Central government 5-6 hundred thousand migrant labourers move strenuously to reach their villages; due to unemployability, lack of availability of food. Transportation was also not available so thousands of workers stuck at various stations.

One controversial incidence was there on many of migrant labourers through pipe disinfectant sprayed that might cause to their immunity and many due to exhaustion of long journey or run over by vehicles and died too. (HRW 2020). Most of poor families in Asia live in slums, which have lots of migrant workers and for higher wages and more work opportunities they frequently move to cities that are nearby or far away from their slums were affected a lot. Then comes threat to slum dwellers, in India around 22% population lives in urban slums, face many issues related to acute poverty, overcrowding (social distancing not followed properly), vulnerable public health setups, unhygienic and unhealthy residing conditions (increase threat to be in contact with SARS-COV patient). For instance, Dharavi slums of Mumbai. Next worst affected population category in COVID-19 outbreak is daily wage earners, livelihood loss, some might run out of food. Many don't have bank accounts so they were not getting benefits from schemes started by government. Although those schemes were not reaching to every household, so during lockdown they had to go out to take daily commodities and face beatings from local police as they also had to follow proper guidelines during lockdown. Other categories like domestic helpers who fall under category of informally paid work, due to this pandemic many left unemployable and most of them unable to feed their families and not able to come up with daily needs. Mid-day meal in schools also closed during lockdown which affects children a lot and also some of these lower-middle-class communities also lack useful resources and network connectivity which affects their study a lot during online classes (Chotiner 2020). Lockdown also affects farmers, as there was drastic change in demands in market was decreased. For instance, triggered problems for farmers in Assam as around 75% (~ 3.10 crore) population. As many farmers also had to payback their agricultural loan, which leads to difficulty in their livelihood. And around 60

million people of entertainment industry were highly affected due to lockdown in India. Many individuals lived without any source of income, 10 million people were at risk of losing their livelihoods (Chotiner 2020).

Continent-Africa

By 2020 April Mid, at almost all African countries faces arrival of COVID-19. In fast emerging country named as Ghana, in early April, 1000+ cases were reported of new corona virus pandemic. To overcome from pandemic most of countries in sub-Saharan Africa follow other continents and restraint their countries and started blockade which leads to high poverty which was faced by many daily wage workers (African Union 2020). Within weeks virus spread to dozens of countries, and all health officials and government trying to limit viral infection (WHO 2020). This pandemic left African countries in huge poverty and loss of economy few countries like Benin, Chad, and Niger.

In Nigeria, more than 200 millions of residents were under poverty. Mortality rate was around 3.6% in Africa, mostly in patients of diabetes, hypertension, asthma or aged persons (above 60). For individuals who aged above 70, more affected around 2 in 10 of confirmed cases lose their lives (Worldmeter 2020). To minimize risk of infection and transmission of disease proper guidelines were followed and proper concern to personal hygiene, frequent hand wash and use of sanitizers. Major issue was negative impacts on socio-economic effect which hardens survival of poor. So, to fight against this negative impact international organisations including Union of Africa, developed various programs to ensure food supplement, medical help, and financial support for needy individuals of Africa.

Continent- South America

In America, major countries faced poverty was Brazil and Argentina. Although frequent response and support to poor and emphasize social isolation. The President of Brazil to minimize effects of virus assumes negotiations stance (Alessi 2020). Since economic team took weeks to install policies to guarantee minimum income for poorest people, technical and ethical fragility (express its inability to manage in COVID crisis) revealed during COVID-19. By Brazilian government some restrictive and preventive measures adopted such as Laboratory support, Infection control measures, surveillance, Pharmaceutical assistance, health assessment, risk management etc, but on one side challenges of poor go beyond this. Macedon et.al, highlighted lack of general sanitation, and many of restrictive measures were less effective. Communication within government and between population and government, shows not proper clarification and by media there is manipulation of leaving poor population confused and with more vulnerability, on Brazil country there was more affect of coronavirus pandemic (Jimenez & Mendonca 2020). In current scenario, South America faced many obstacles to get overcome from pandemic, not only the issue of poverty along with that management crisis to deal with issue of public health.

Continent: Europe

In certain European regions, there was a huge impact on healthcare system, economies, household's income, welfare, employment and many more unexpected impacts (European commission, 2020). More number of positive cases of COVID-19 leads to significant decrement in agricultural activities, trade, tourism and industries. Compare to middle February stock market of Europe fall around 30%.Data collected from European Trade Union Confederation, was that in two weeks approximately 1 million

persons left unemployable. To overcome from this economic crisis countries of Europe was looking for solutions. Four priorities pointed out by European Council that is internal market functioning, massive investment strategy, EU external actions and resilience and governance. Simultaneous efforts of European commission as well as NGOs to support citizens, companies and economies of members of countries (European commission, 2020).

Integrative Review method an introduction

It can be defined as an international reputation practice for evidence based study. Integrative review also made for investigate synthesis and analysis of collective information of primary data. It also helps to analysis exploitation of research dimensions. It is helpful tool to solve issues from secondary data and create new theories and approaches. It's provides a systematic representation of data and research (Crossetti 2012). The min motive of the IR is to retrieving the old data and focus to find new problem resolving theories and practices. So the topic of COVID -19 is major concern to be resolve in terms of poverty and unemployment. It is allowing to an answer some particular type of questions and conclusions to be sought out related problems. The IR retrieving found what is known and what should be known. Therefore with the help of IR synthesis of problem rising can be resolved. This review is based upon the strategies and data that will helpful to estimate the actual rate of poverty lead to unemployment. Therefore both types of qualitative and quantitative researches have involved to find out the outcome of all pervious collection of data in comprehensive analysis (Crosetti 2012). According to the Insert Date of Search literature survey had conducted by using electronic database called EMBASE and LILACS. It has been developed by a specialist researcher and found first 1000 of research according to American journal of economics 2020.

Conclusion:

COVID-19 has a strong impact on economy of any country and in 2020 in every country. The criteria of the study selection is based upon the data that carried out for extraction and two authors will examine individually. If there will be any conflict comes from third author then it can be solves by mutual discussions. The points involved in it-1.abstract should be visible 2. Should be published in English, Portuguese and Spanish to evaluate and investigate problems in case of COVID-19. By combining all the studies it will be lead to make conclusion of problems of COVID-19. In a country all the action involved to the public health is related to administrative orders according to the political responses. Economical responses is depend upon the way that how the political authorities behaving for that particular matter. Lack of social responses to problems led to major destruction of economic crisis. Fake support also doesn't define any public support and conclusion. In the last it will be concluded that political authorities re more responsible foe economy of a country. According to the WHO the basic necessities should be free to the local government like masks, disinfectants, detergents, ethanol, sanitizers etc.

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